

**THE PROBLEM OF TRANSLATING DERIVED NOUNS WITH THE SUFFIX
“-MAN” (FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK)**

Scientific adviser: Phd Xudoynazarova O'g'lanoy Allamurodovna

Ruxshona Abdujalilova Abdug'afforzoda

1st course master, Termez State University, Uzbekistan

Abstract.

Introduction. *This article provides information on the linguistic features of derived noun units in linguistics. Derived nouns are differentiated from compound nouns by giving the facts. It has been proved by examples that derived nouns formed by the suffix “man”, represent a person in a special activity, a person of a specific character, Together with this knowledge, the article analyzes the alternative translations of derived nouns and interpretation procedures based on examples, which may be difficult in the translation process.*

Key words. *Nouns, derived nouns, affixes, suffixes, translating problems, complex nouns, compound nouns.*

**ПРОБЛЕМА ПЕРЕВОДА ПРОИЗВОДНЫХ СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ С
СУФФИКСОМ «MAN» (С АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ)**

Рухшона Абдужалилова Абдузаффорзода

*Научный руководитель: Док. Фил. Наука Худойназарова Ўзганой
Алламуродовна*

Магистр 1 курса, Термезский Государственный Университет, Узбекистан.

Аннотация

Введение: *В данной статье представлена информация о языковых особенностях производных именных единиц в языкознании. Производные существительные отличаются от сложных существительных тем, что сообщают факты. На примерах доказано, что производные существительные, образованные суффиксом «-man», обозначают человека в особой деятельности, человека определенного характера, стоящего в определенном положении, классифицируемого по выражению его национальности. Вместе с этими знаниями в статье анализируются альтернативные переводы производных существительных и процедуры толкования на примерах, которые могут быть затруднены в процессе перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *существительные, производные существительные, аффиксы, суффиксы, проблемы перевода, сложные существительные, составные существительные.*

**“MAN” QO'SHIMCHASI BILAN YASALGAN YASAMA OTLARNING
TARJIMADAGI MUOMMOSI (INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARI TALQINIDA)**

Ruxshona Abdujalilova Abdug'afforzoda

Ilmiy rahbar: Phd Xudoynazarova O'g'lanoy Allamurodovna

1-kurs magistr, Termiz Davlat Universiteti, Uzbekiston.

Abstrakt qismi

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola tilshunoslikda yasama ot birliklarining lisoniy xususiyatlari haqida ma'lumot beradi. Yasama otlarning qo'shma otlardan o'zaro farq qilishi asoslab berilgan. "man" so'z yasovchi qo'shimchasi orqali yasalgan yasama otlarning maxsus faoliyatdagi shaxs, o'ziga xos xarakterga ega shaxs, ma'lum pozitsiyada turganlini ifodalinishi, millatini ifodalinishiga ko'ra tasniflanishi misollar bilan dalillab berilgan. Shu bilan birgalikda, maqolada tarjima jarayonida qiyinchilikka uchrashi mumkin bo'lgan yasama so'zlarning muqobil tarjimalarini va izoh berish tartiblari misollar asosida tushuntirilib tahlil qilingan.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *otlar, yasama otlar, affikslar, qo'shimchalar, saffikslar, tarjima masalalari, murakkab otlar, qo'shma otlar.*

A **noun** (from [Latin](#) *nōmen* 'name') is a [word](#) that functions as the name of a specific object or set of objects, such as living creatures, places, actions, qualities, states of existence, or ideas. However, *noun* is not a [semantic](#) category, so it cannot be characterized in terms of its meaning. Nouns have sometimes been defined in terms of the grammatical categories to which they are subject (classed by gender, inflected for case and number). Such definitions tend to be language-specific, since nouns do not have the same categories in all languages.³² Nouns are studied by many linguists. They are A. Gupta, W. Croft, Mark Baker, Joshua S. Guenter, P. Geach, Laycock Henry, A. Barbara Kaiser, C. Cheryl Zoll, Hagit Borer, Lester Mark, Beason Larry, Marga Reimer, N. Edward and A. T. Irisqulov, Л. Бархударов, М. Блох, В.В. Виноградов, А. Смирницкий, . В. Khaimovich and others. Nouns are characterized by three criteria: **semantic** (meaning), **morphological** (form and grammatical categories) and **syntactical** (functions, distributions). According to morphological features, nouns can be:

- Simple, derived (stem + affix or affix + stem)
- Compound (stem + stem)
- Composite

Derived nouns are nouns which adding any specific affix in order to create new meaning or adding extra meaning to the stem. According to David Crystal: "*Derivational morphology* studies the principles governing the construction of new words, without reference to the specific grammatical role a word might play in a sentence. In the formation of *drinkable* from *drink*, or *disinfect* from *infect*, for example, we see the formation of new words, each with its own grammatical properties."³³ Geert Booij said about derivation: "Morphological patterns that can be systematically extended are called *productive*. The derivation of nouns ending in *-er* from verbs is productive in

³² Charlton T. Lewis and Charles Short. [A Latin Dictionary](#) on [Perseus Project](#).

³³ David Crystal. *How language works*. – Overlook Press, 2005.

English, but the derivation of nouns in *-th* from adjectives is not: it is hard to expand the set of words of this type such as *depth, health, length, strength, and wealth*. Marchand (1969: 349) has observed some occasional coinings like *coolth* (after *warmth*) but notes that such word coinings are often jocular, and hence do not represent a productive pattern. If we want to coin a new English noun on the basis of an adjective, we have to use *-ness* or *-ity* instead."³⁴

Basic difference between derived nouns and compound nouns is that even though derived nouns has more than 2 affixes they can not be stem and can not mean another meaning without stem of the word. But in compound words they consist of two or more than two stems that have each own meaning. When it is separated from each other, they can mean something alone. Because compound nouns consist of independent nouns which have own meanings. Such as:

Manage + ment = management (derived noun with the suffix -ment)

In + dependent = independent (derived noun with the prefix in-)

Lady + bird = ladybird (compound noun with two stems: lady and bird)

Five-year-old girl. (a compound noun consists of three stems with hyphens)

Derived nouns can be created by prefixes and suffixes. Here are some types of derived nouns:

- Agent nouns (agent nouns are usually made from verbs into nouns adding suffixes: *bake – baker*)
- Abstract nouns (such as: *- dom, free + dom, freedom, -ness dark + ness = darkness*)
- Concrete nouns (for instance: *- ant/-ent student, assistant; -ix proprietrix*)

Creating derived nouns, prefixes and suffixes stand basic role. In linguistics, **Suffixes** are classified the type of affix and they are placed at the end of stem of a word. One of the most noticeable definition of suffix was given by Marchand: “A suffix is a bound morpheme which in a syntagma AB occupies the position B.” (Marchand 1969, 209.). Common examples are case endings, grammatical case of nouns, adjectives, verb endings (conjugation).³⁵ The most attentional features of suffixes are that they can carry both grammatical information and lexical information. Derivational suffixes are divided into two categories:

- class changing derivation (*play -player; verb-noun*)

³⁴ Geert Booij, *The Grammar of words: An introduction to linguistic morphology*. Oxford University Press, 2005.

³⁵ Marchand, Hans. *The categories and types of present-day English word-formation: A synchronic-diachronic approach*. – Munich: Beck, 1969. pp. 356

- class maintaining derivation (*friend – friendship; noun – noun*)

There are two types of suffixes:

- Derivational suffix: by the helping of these types of suffixes, one can change the stem meaning of word and create a new meaning on behalf of its previous meaning. For example: *clean – cleaner; clean means to tidy the mess of somewhere but cleaner means that someone who cleans somewhere*. Moreover, it can make the word a different part of speech. Such as: *-ly* is usually added for adjective in order to make the adjective an adverb. *Polite – politely*. In this situation, the suffixes can not create a new meaning but it can change the speech from an adjective to an adverb.
- Inflectional suffix: it transforms the base word into a different tense without changing its meaning. Let's take *-s* as an example, *-s* is used for nouns to explore the number of noun. *A dog – dogs* inflectional suffix *-s* doesn't change meaning. The meaning of the word 'dog' is still the same but the number of word is changed.

The suffix 'man' is one of the derivational suffixes that has several meaning and are used in several ways for saying the person's position/character/ability/profession and others. It can be a new branch of linguistics called **feminist linguistics**. The fact is that a new direction has appeared in linguistics in recent decades - feminist linguistics or feminist criticism of language (Hughes, 1989; Lakoff, 1975; Maggio, 1987; Mills, 1989). The object of study of FL is all words and forms that serve as means of indicating whether a person belongs to the male or female sex.

Among the units of language that are subject to feminist criticism, within the framework of the studied SG, the following can be mentioned:

- noun man in their LSV "man (without indicating age and gender) - Every man is the architect of his fortune; and "humanity" - Man has built magnificent civilizations in the deserts; - derived words (derivatives and composites) with the root stem man, the motivating basis for the formation of which was the LSV shall "man" and "humanity": mankind, manlike, man (v), manned, man-made, man-hole, manpower and others; - words with the *-man* semi-suffix used to designate professions: fireman, mailman, policeman, businessman, chairman, congressman, etc.

Supporters of FL recommend avoiding the use of these words in speech, replacing them with synonymous language units, for example: - a man (person) - a person, an individual, a human being, one; - man (humanity) - humankind, all people, all humans, everybody; - manly - strong, brave, determined, coxirageous; - man (v) - fimiish with people, staff, crew; - policeman - police-officer, law enforcement, etc.

The origin of this suffix is the noun 'man' then the noun has been used as a suffix. It has got plural and feminine forms: - men and – woman/ - women. It is used in these situations:

The examples which stated above are possible implied male. The additional meaning of the example words are the person who is a man not a woman. If the person in the positions is

Someone who is an expert or participate in specific activity	Someone who has specific position	Someone who has specific characteristics in an	Someone who is in a particular nationality	Someone who is in a ship which has special characteristics relating to an area.
<i>seman</i>	<i>man</i>	<i>eman</i>	<i>chman</i>	<i>enlandman</i>
<i>artsman</i>	<i>sman</i>	<i>erman</i>	<i>lishman</i>	<i>Indiaman</i>

female, it can be changed by using – woman. Such as: *horsewoman*, *Englishwoman*, *superwoman*, *sportswoman* and so on. In Uzbek language the most alternative variation of the suffix ‘man’ is ‘-chi’. But, it is not appropriate to use the alternative translation ‘-chi’ for all the derived nouns with ‘man’. Because, the suffix ‘man’ is used many situations that can not be translated using just ‘-chi’ and one have to give definitions or short explanations about the specific word or another alternative words or suffixes in Uzbek language.

For example: *Englishman* – *ingliz odami, angliyalik*;

Horseman – *ot boquvchi, ot mutaxassisi*;

Freeman – *erkin odam, ozod odam*

Iceman - *muz odam*

Gunman – *qurolli odam*

Committeeman – *qo'mita a'zosi*

On the other hand, it can be easily translated with the suffix -chi into Uzbek language:

<i>ker</i>	<i>hi</i>
<i>man</i>	<i>gizchi</i>
<i>eyman</i>	<i>inchi</i>
<i>sman</i>	<i>archi</i>
<i>artsman</i>	<i>rtchi</i>
<i>lman</i>	<i>htachi/xabarchi</i>
<i>man</i>	<i>o'chiruvchi</i>
<i>lman</i>	<i>nirchi</i>

orman	ogchi/bo'yoqchi
o'man	o'pchi
mulanceman	yordamchi

Some of the derived nouns which used 'man' suffix has got specific feature which means specific position or specific place in somewhere/a family:

Clansman – urug' a'zori (it means someone who is a member of the family)

Clergyman – ruhoniy (it is specific position of a person related to his religion)

Armyman – xarbiy xizmatdagi askar/ askar (special temporary position)

Congressman – Kongress a'zosi (special position)

Councilman – Kengash a'zosi (special position)

Dietman – dietolog (it is a profession)

Doorsman – eshik og'asi (it is a profession)

Estatesman – mulkdor shaxs (it is according to his living condition)

In English language, there are some words that we can come across them, they are not derived nouns they are stems but they seem like derived nouns with the suffix 'man'. In these conditions, such kind of words are classified as an international words and can not be translated into Uzbek language. Here are some examples:

Zeeman – is the effect of splitting of a spectral line into several components in the presence of a static magnatic field. (Zeeman effekti magnit maydon ta'sirida atomlar spektrlarining ajralishi hodisasi)³⁶

Ombudsman – is an official who is charged with representing the interests of the public by investigating and addressing complaints of maladministration or a violation of rights. (turli xil ma'muriy organlar ba'zi shaxslar yoki birlashmalarning inson huquqlariga rioya etish va himoya qilish uchun saylangan shaxs)³⁷.

We can say as a **conclusion** that, Translator may face several challenges while translating derivational words into the target language because of its cultural differences and not being aware of linguistic differences. Sometimes derived nouns can not be translated into the target language and sometimes there is no alternative translation in the target language and in that case translator has to give definition or explanation about the derived noun in the target language. So that one must be careful what it means, how it is used, for whom are used (male or female), it is an international word or not.

³⁶ Preston, Thomas Radiation Phenomena in a strong magnetic field. *The Scientific Transactions of the Royal Dublin Society*. 1898, pp 385–342.

³⁷ Sattorov A. Ombudsman – huquq himoyachisi. T., 2000.

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